

The HuT

Consortium meetings n.4

Deliverable D7.9

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.5 Consortium meetings

AUTHORS

Michele Calvello (UNISA); Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA)

Version 1.0

(29 December 2025)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101073957

1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
Project Title	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
Project Coordinator	Michele Calvello UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO mcalvello@unisa.it
Project Duration	October 2022 – September 2026 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D7.9
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP7 - Coordination and Management
Task	T7.5 - Consortium meetings
Lead beneficiary	UNISA
Contributing beneficiary/ies	

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	18.12.2025	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	First draft
0.2	19.12.2025	Guido Rianna (CMCC)	Critical review and proofreading
1.0	29.12.2025	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Final version

2. Table of contents

1. Technical references	2
1.1. Document history	3
2. Table of contents	4
2.1. List of Tables	4
2.2. List of Figures	4
3. Annual meeting in Germany	5
3.1. Location and participants	5
3.2. Agenda	7
3.3. Activities.....	8
3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs) and thematic discussions	8
3.3.2. Demonstrators (DEMs).....	9
3.3.3. International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) workshop	9
3.3.4. General Assembly.....	9
3.3.5. Concluding remarks	11

2.1. List of Tables

Table 1: Participant list.....	5
Table 2: Participants in General Assembly.....	10

2.2. List of Figures

none

3. Annual meeting in Germany

3.1. Location and participants

The HuT end-of-year-three consortium meeting has been held in Germany on September 22-24, 2025, in different locations of Hamburg and Glückstadt as follows:

- Hamburg: GERICS Headquarter Chilehaus (Monday 22 September)
- Glückstadt: various locations (Tuesday 23 September)
- Hamburg: Hafencity University Hamburg (Wednesday 24 September)

Table 1: Participant list

ID	Acronym	Name	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1	UNISA	Michele Calvello	yes	yes	yes
1	UNISA	Gaetano Pecoraro	yes	yes	yes
2	CMCC	Guido Rianna	yes	yes	yes
2.1	CNR	Valentina Bacciu	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Anke Schluensen-Rico	yes	yes	yes
4	GFZ	Laurens Oostwegel	yes	yes	yes
4	GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Marcel Hurlimann	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Alex Flavio Asurza	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Adria Rubio-Martin	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Ana Gabriela Fernandez Garca	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Eric Gielen	yes	yes	yes
8	NGI	Luca Piciullo	yes	yes	yes
8	NGI	Graham Lewis Gilbert	yes	yes	yes
9	GWP-CEE	Stanislav Hronček	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir		yes	yes
11	IMO	Jón Kristinn Helgason		yes	yes
12	VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius	yes	yes	yes

12	VU	Giedre Godiene	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Francis Nieto Torres	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Quique Vidal	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Katona Péter Gergő		yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Harsányi Gábor		yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Sólyom Péter		yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Vizi Dávid Béla		yes	yes
15	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti	yes	yes	yes
15	ICONS	Erica Moresco	yes	yes	yes
15	ICONS	Eylul Aksekili	yes	yes	yes
18	CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu	yes	yes	yes
18	CONF-NO	Giuseppe Demelas	yes	yes	yes
18	CONF-NO	Michele Arcangelo Ena	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Elias Huland	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Mario Bruno Rohrer	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Anna Scolobig	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Markus Stoffel	yes	yes	yes
23	MET	Robert Neal	yes	yes	yes
24	BGS	Katy Freeborough	yes	yes	yes
25	GNDR	Shivangi Chavda	yes	yes	yes

Note: Other people from consortium partners attended online on Monday 22 and Wednesday 24 September.

3.2. Agenda

Monday 22 September

Hamburg: GERICS Headquarter Chilehaus

- 08:45 – 09:45
Scientific Coordination Team meeting
(only WP Leaders)
- 09:45 – 10:15
Arrival of other participants & welcome coffee
- 10:15 – 12:15. SESSION 1
part 1) KER workshop
part 2) General Assembly: GANTT of activities and financial reporting for each partner, deliverables, KPIs, next Annual Meeting
- Lunch
- 13:15 – 15:15. SESSION 2
Thematic discussion #1: Serious game, educational material, virtual field visits
Thematic discussion #2: Web portals and data repositories
Thematic discussion #3: Amplification
Thematic discussion #4: Policy briefs
- Coffee break
- 15:45 – 17:45. SESSION 3
Plenary discussion on other topics
Networking between partners
- Consortium Dinner

Tuesday 23 September

Glückstadt: various locations

- 09:30 – 10:40. Welcome by Mayor and initial presentations
Jugendzentrum Glückstadt
- 11:00 – 14:30. Art exhibition and other activities (including lunch)
Palais für aktuelle Kunst, PaK (web site: <https://pak-glueckstadt.de/>)
- 14:30 – 16:00. Walking field visit
- 16:00 – 18:00. Meeting with municipality and other stakeholders (including coffee break)
Jugendzentrum Glückstadt
- Consortium Dinner

Wednesday 24 September

Hamburg: HafenCity University Hamburg (HCU)

The HuT I-DRRnF “International Systemic Risk Conference”

co-organized with the Cluster of Excellence Climate, Climatic Change, and Society (CLICCS), with support from WCRP (Safe Landing Climates), UNDRR, ASRA and the Knowledge-Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events (Risk KAN)

- 9:00 – 9:20. Welcome address
- 9:20 – 12:15. Plenary invited presentations (including coffee break)
- 12:15 – 13:00. Innovation Fair “Demonstrators’ Arena showcase posters”
Flagship activities will be showcased by topic, according to the scheme that we are using for the progress meetings (former DMB-CDE meetings). The aim is for The HuT consortium to present to an external audience the main innovations that are being implemented in the DEM territories within The HuT.
- Lunch
- 14:00 – 17:00. Plenary invited presentations (including coffee break)
- 17:00 – 18:30. Panel discussion
- 18:30 – 20:00. Networking session with drinks and finger food

3.3. Activities

All the activities listed on the Agenda have been carried out. The presentations are shared internally using the google drive platform (see Deliverable 7.6 – Data management plan n.2, <https://zenodo.org/records/15109420>)

3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs) and thematic discussions

The activities that are being conducted in the seven WPs were initially discussed during a Scientific Coordination Team meeting, attended only by the coordinator and the other WP Leaders. The main aim of this initial session was to highlight potential major problems with the progress of the tasks conducted in the WPs, with special attention devoted to the deliverables to submit in the third and final reporting term. No major problems were identified by the WP leaders during this initial session.

During the first day of the meeting, the following thematic discussions were carried out.

1. Key exploitable results
2. Serious game, educational material, virtual field visits
3. Web portals and data repositories
4. Amplification strategy
5. Policy briefs

3.3.2. Demonstrators (DEMs)

A poster session on the third day of the meeting was specifically devoted to the 10 Demonstrators

DEM 1 – Valencia (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, heatwaves.

DEM 2 – Val d’Aran Region (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, floods, forest fires, landslides.

DEM 3 – Lattari mountains (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: floods, forest fires, landslides, storms.

DEM 4 – Vilnius (Lithuania). Investigated climate extremes: floods.

DEM 5 – Schleswig-Holstein State (Germany).

DEM 6 – East fjords (Iceland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides.

DEM 7 – Tisza River Basin (Hungary). Investigated climate extremes: floods.

DEM 8 – Ogliastra (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, forest fires, heatwaves.

DEM 9 – Dorset (UK). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms.

DEM 10 – Berne Canton (Switzerland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms.

The DEM leaders presented their flagship activities by means of posters that were exposed and discussed during a session that was attended by all the participants to the International Systemic Risk Conference, and not only by the members of the consortium. The aim was for The HuT consortium to present to an external audience the main innovations that are being implemented in the DEM territories within the project, in the form of an “Innovation Fair.”

The entire second day of the meeting was devoted to a field trip in the city of Gluckstadt, which is the municipality of the Schleswig-Holstein State where most of the DEM 5 activities are being carried out. The field trip was planned, organized and conducted to fulfill two complementary aims: allow the partners of the consortium to get firsthand impressions of the DEM 5 territory and actors involved in the project activities; allow the main German stakeholders involved in DEM 5 activities to meet and interact with consortium members.

3.3.3. International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) workshop

The third day of the meeting was devoted to the third edition of the International DRR Nexus Forum workshops, in the form of an “International Systemic Risk Conference” co-organized with the Cluster of Excellence Climate, Climatic Change, and Society (CLICCS), with support from WCRP (Safe Landing Climates), UNDRR, ASRA and the Knowledge-Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events (Risk KAN).

More details on the Conference are available in deliverable D.5.8 - “Minutes from the I-DRRnF workshops n.3”.

3.3.4. General Assembly

The fourth General Assembly of The HuT was held on Monday 22 September 2025, during the first day of the meeting. Table 2 shows the list of participants.

Table 2: Participants in General Assembly

Partner	Name
UNISA	Michele Calvello
CMCC	Guido Rianna
CNR	Valentina Bacciu
HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer
IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer (online)
UPC	Marcel Hurlimann
UPV	Adria Rubio-Martin
NGI	Luca Piciullo
GWP-CEE	Stanislav Hronček
HY	Sirkku Juhola (online)
IMO	(apologies)
VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius
ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet
KOTIVIZIG	(apologies)
ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti
LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti (online)
SOR	(apologies)
CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu
NIP	(apologies)
MA	(apologies)
UNIGE	Anna Scolobig
UCL	Carina Fearnley (online)
MET	Robert Neal
BGS	Katy Freeborough
GNDR	Shivangi Chavda

The General Assembly has mainly addressed the financial reporting of the partners and the schedule of deliverables, confirming that the project is progressing as planned and there isn't any need to implement mitigation measures. The General Assembly has given mandate to coordinator, deputy coordinator and project manager, to organize the final review meeting with the project officer and the two reviewers in presence during the last The HuT annual meeting, which will be held in Napoli (Italy) at the end of June 2026.

3.3.5. Concluding remarks

Based on what was presented and discussed over the three days, the partnership did not identify any specific critical issue. The activity plan up to the end of the project and the final review meeting, to be conducted with the project officer and the two reviewers in presence during the last The HuT annual meeting in Napoli (Italy) at the end of June 2026, has been agreed upon and defined. The deliverables and the activities to be carried out in the coming months are expected to proceed as planned.

